

The reality of the process of sports selection for school teams in handball from the point of view of physical education teachers

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Abstract

The Object of the study aims to identify the reality of the sports selection process for school teams in handball from the point of view of physical education teachers, for this purpose, we used the descriptive method on a sample composed of 50 physical education teachers. Chosen as randomly, and for data collection, we used a questionnaire After collecting the results and having treated them statistically, we conclude that the process of sports selection for the school teams is subject to the foundations and scientific standards by the physical education teacher, in addition to that there are no statistically significant differences between the teachers of physical education in the selection process for the school teams in handball due to the professional experience. On this basis, the study recommended that it is necessary to improve working conditions for physical education teachers by providing all the capabilities and means required by the selection process for school teams.

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1. Introduction

School sports is the only activity that cares for elite pupils in the sports field, each according to his abilities, aptitudes, and inclinations, so it takes the first steps and correct guidance in order to reach high performance (Houlihan & Green, 2006).

The process of correct guidance for the pupil depends on the selection process, as it is a process that requires finding individuals in a large community who are highly skilled in one of the types of sport (Abduhamidovich et al., 2022).

Educational institutions are a source for gifted pupils, as the teacher of physical and sports education is responsible for selecting them and discovering their preparations at an early age, which is the backbone of the educational process in the physical education class (Siedentop et al., 2019); the physical education teacher works hard to organize sports groups according to individual differences, trying to attract pupils' interests towards the activity they prefer, especially in adolescence (Pangrazi & Beighl, 2019).

In developed countries, physical education occupies a prominent place in school programs due to the gains that can be achieved by studying physical education and sports and its complementary activities (Kirk, 2018).

School activities are a fertile ground for nurturing and discovering the outstanding students, if they are exploited appropriately. A little interest in school activities will save a lot of time, effort and money in caring for the outstanding towards what is desired (Strandbu et al., 2019).

Many previous studies highlighted the role of the teacher of physical education in the selection process, which is considered one of the difficult tasks that allow him to choose and discover the best athletes in a specialized sports field, where he must select the pupils in proportion to the type of sports activity that is compatible with his abilities, capabilities and various preparations. Physical education teachers and coaches rely on many physical, skill and cognitive tests for the success of the selection of players (Lidor et al., 2009). The experience of the physical education teacher

facilitates the process of selecting players in the school teams, as well as providing the means and sports facilities (Lugo et al.,2004). The physical education teacher and coach discovers young talents who will be among the elite in the future (Güllich & Emrich, 2006). Despite the role played by the teacher of physical education in discovering young talents, he sometimes does not rely on scientific foundations. The reason may be due to the lack of time and the capabilities in the institutions and the lack of qualified managers (Kirk,2005; Lam et al.,2019).

Based on what has been presented in theoretical literature about the process of sports selection and clarifying the physical education teacher's role and responsibilities towards the selection process in the educational environment, so the current study aims to identify the reality of the sports selection process for school teams in handball from the point of view of physical education teachers .

2. Method and Materials

2.1. Participants

The sample of the study was limited to physical education teachers in the intermediate education stage in the city of Ouargla, and their number is estimated at 50 teachers, which represents 45.47% of the study population, where there are 115 teachers in the state(wilaya) of Ouargla, and the table 01 shows the distribution of the study sample according to years of experience.

2.2. Materials

In order to identify the process of sports selection for school teams in handball, a tool was built, which includes (42) items distributed over four axes (the selection process for school teams in handball based on scientific foundations and criteria, the formation of physical education teacher is not sufficient to carry out the selection process, physical education teacher has sufficient capabilities for the selection process for school teams in handball, physical education teacher faces some obstacles in the selection process for

school teams in handball-Table02). For an answer that is (yes or no), alternatives (2, 1) were given, respectively.

Table No.02 shows the axes and number of items of the study tool.

N	The questionnaire axes	Numbers of items
1	the selection process for school teams in handball based on scientific foundations and criteria	12
2	the formation of physical education teacher is not sufficient to carry out the selection process	10
3	physical education teacher has sufficient capabilities for the selection process for school teams in handball	10
4	physical education teacher faces some obstacles in the selection process for school teams in handball	10
	Total	42

Discriminatory validity using peripheral comparison method confirmed that the questionnaire has high validity; This is what the results of Table 3 show.

Table No.03: The validity of the questionnaire is represented by the peripheral comparison validity method

Group	N	Mean	SD	T-Test	DF	Sing
The lowest	05	1.41	0.09	6.24	8	0.05
The highest	05	1.69	0.03			

The value of the stability coefficient, Cronbach's alpha, was 0.75, which confirms the stability of the resolution.

2.3. Statistical Analysis

The SPSS statistical package was used, and it included: The means, Standard deviation, T-test for two independent samples and One-way analysis of variance (F) test.

3. Results

The first hypothesis: The selection process for school teams in handball is not subject to scientific foundations and criteria

Table No. 4: represents the values of the means and standard deviations for the first axis

N°	Items	Mean	SD	Ranking	Level
1	Do you do tests during the selection process?	1.80	0.40	4	High
2	Do you take into account the principle of individual differences in selection?	1.86	0.35	1	High
3	Do you attach great importance to the (psychological, technical, physical, morphological) aspect of the selection process?	1.82	0.38	2	High
4	Do you think that the intermediate education stage is suitable for the selection process?	1.74	0.44	6	High
5	Do all stages of the selection process apply?	1.46	0.50	12	Low
6	Do you apply selection criteria in handball?	1.58	0.49	9	High
7	Do you take into account selection determinants?	1.72	0.45	7	High
8	Do you think that the factor of age and heredity is important in the selection process?	1.76	0.43	5	High
9	Do you think there are factors that determine the success of applying scientific foundations in the selection process?	1.82	0.38	2	High
10	Do you rely on modern technologies in the selection process?	1.46	0.50	11	Low
11	Do you rely on morphological (entropometric) measurements in the selection process?	1.50	0.50	10	Low
12	Do you rely on specific methods during the selection process?	1.64	0.48	8	High
Total		1.86	0.26		High

It is clear from table (04) that there is a consensus in the responses of the participants that the selection process for school teams in handball is subject to scientific foundations and criteria, as the levels of the items were (1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 12) of the points of view of physical education teachers is high, them means ranged between (M=1.58, – M=1.86).

The second hypothesis: The formation of physical education teacher is not enough to carry out the selection process

Table No. 05: represents the values of the means and standard deviations for the second axis

N°	Items	Mean	SD	Ranking	Level
1	Did you do a special formation in the selection process?	1.22	0.41	9	Low
2	Have you participated in forums and courses on sports selection?	1.36	0.48	7	Low
3	Do you carry out the selection process for students with high qualities?	1.62	0.49	3	Very high
4	Did you include the topic of sports selection in the seminars with the inspector?	1.24	0.43	8	Low
5	Does your continuous formation about the selection process have a role in selecting the best elements?	1.64	0.48	2	High
6	Does your experience as a teacher influence the selection process?	1.68	0.47	1	Very high
7	Are you familiar with the modern foundations of the selection process?	1.58	0.49	4	Very high
8	Does your formation make you see that the selection process takes place through one competition?	1.12	0.32	10	Low
9	Does your lack of formation make you see that the selection process is a complex one?	1.50	0.50	6	Low
10	Does your continuous formation enable you to become the first person responsible for the selection process?	1.52	0.50	5	High
Total		1.44	0.19		Low

The results of the means and standard deviations in Table No. 05 display that the physical education teacher's level of training is insufficient to carry out the selection process is low. Although the phrases (3, 5, 6, 7, 10) were of high level; The means ranged between (1.52-1.68).

The third hypothesis: The physical education teacher does not have sufficient capabilities for the selection process for school teams in handball.

Table No. 06: represents the values of the means and standard deviations for the third axis.

N°	Items	Mean	SD	Ranking	Level
1	Does the lack of sports facilities negatively affect the selection process for school teams?	1.88	0.32	1	High
2	Are the means and equipment in line with the number of pupils in your institution?	1.24	0.43	9	Low
3	Are there playgrounds and equipment for handball in your educational institution?	1.34	0.47	6	Low
4	Do you find help from your community during the selection process?	1.36	0.48	5	Low
5	Is the budget allocated for physical education sufficient to meet your needs?	1.18	0.38	10	Low
6	Do you have the devices and pedagogical means for individual and group activities?	1.26	0.44	8	Low
7	Do you maintain sports equipment inside the institution?	0.47	0.49	4	Very high
8	Does the institution provide you with medical supplies during the selection process?	0.46	0.32	7	Low
9	Do material capabilities affect the application of scientific foundations in the selection process?	0.45	0.50	3	High
10	Does modern equipment and means facilitate and speed up the selection process?	0.37	0.50	2	High
Total		1.48	0.18		Low

It is clear from the data of table (6) that the items of the third axis directed to teachers of physical education and sports in the selection process for school teams in handball that the level of capabilities and facilities available to conduct the selection process is low. Most of the items (2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 8) were at a low level; the means ranged between (1.18 - 1.34).

The fourth hypothesis: The teacher of physical education faces some obstacles in the selection process for the school teams in handball.

Table No. 07: represents the values of the mean

N°	Items	Mean	SD	Ranking	Level
1		1.70	0.45	2	Very high
2	Are the means and equipment in line with the number of pupils in your institution?	1.90	0.30	1	High
3	Are there playgrounds and equipment for handball in your educational institution?	1.60	0.49	4	High
4	Do you find help from your community during the selection process?	1.30	0.46	7	Low
5	Is the budget allocated for physical education sufficient to meet your needs?	1.68	0.47	3	Very high
6	Do you have the devices and pedagogical means for individual and group activities?	1.22	0.41	10	Very low
7	Do you maintain sports equipment inside the institution?	1.34	0.47	5	Low
8	Does the institution provide you with medical supplies during the selection process?	1.34	0.47	5	Low
9	Do material capabilities affect the application of scientific foundations in the selection process?	1.24	0.43	9	Low
10	Does modern equipment and means facilitate and speed up the selection process?	1.25	0.44	8	Low
Total		1.45	0.16		Low

s and standard deviations for the fourth axis.

The results listed in Table 7 confirm that physical education teachers face some obstacles in the process of selecting school teams in handball. Most of the item's levels (4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10) were low; Where the means ranged between (1.22 - 1.34).

The fifth hypothesis: There are statistically significant differences between physical education teachers in the selection process due to professional experience.

Table No. 08: Explains the differences between teachers of physical education s in the selection process for school teams

Variable	Years of Experience (years)	N	Means	SD	F	DF	Sing
The first axis	0-5	22	1.63	0.22	1.27	2	0.28
	6-10	10	1.64	0.33			
	More than 11	18	1.75	0.25			
The second axis	0-5	22	1.37	0.13	4.14	2	0.02
	6-10	10	1.45	0.12			
	More than 11	18	1.53	0.24			
The third axis	0-5	22	1.45	0.13	0.43	2	0.65
	6-10	10	1.53	0.20			
	More than 11	18	1.45	0.23			
The fourth axis	0-5	22	1.44	0.15	1.95	2	0.15
	6-10	10	1.55	0.21			
	More than 11	18	1.42	0.14			
Total	0-5	22	1.48	0.12	1.28	2	0.28
	6-10	10	1.54	0.15			
	More than 11	18	1.55	0.17			

After using analysis of variance (one by way ANOVA) in Table No. 8, it was found that there were no statistically significant differences between the physical education teacher according to professional experience in the first, third and fourth axis, while it revealed that there were statistically significant differences in the second axis.

4. Discussion

The physical education teacher believes that the selection process for school teams is subject to foundations and standards because the teacher has tribal gains that she obtains through his formative path or self-training (Gould et al., 1990). Chiva-Bartoll et al (2021) indicated that the teacher makes a

positive impact on the pupil by using scientific methods in the selection process. Seminars and periodic training programs do not focus on the selection process in school teams, which reflects negatively on this process. There is no continuous training in order to know the various knowledge, skills, experiences, techniques and new mechanisms in the field (Lam et al,2019).All physical education teachers emphasize that the capabilities and means that help the smooth running of the selection process are not available. The lack of capabilities, means, facilities, security and safety negatively affects the selection process in school teams (Lidor et al,2009; Lam et al,2019). In addition to the above, other obstacles affect the selection process in school teams. The physical education teacher does not find support from other teachers and administration, and the lack of time allotted for the operation is insufficient, which puts him under pressure (Lugo et al.,2004).

There is no difference between the physical education teachers in the selection process due to professional experience. Because they share the same environmental conditions, work with the same means and capabilities, acquire the same information and experience about the process, and have the same vitality and enthusiasm to achieve the desired goal (Lugo et al.,2004; Kirk,2005). Physical education teachers seek to discover talents at all educational levels that would have the opportunity to join professional teams and represent national teams despite obstacles and difficult circumstances (Bailey & Morley, 2006).

5. Conclusion

In light of the results obtained through the study, it is necessary to improve working conditions for physical education teachers by providing all the capabilities and means required by the selection process for school teams, Improving and diversifying material and moral incentives for physical education teachers to encourage them to work more, and Increasing interest by educational supervisors in the continuous formation of teachers in order

to overcome the difficulties and problems they face in the selection process for school teams.

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